

Optical Resolution of Some α - and γ -Substituted Pyridine Methanols

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Several tertiary alcohols, as listed in Table I, have been successfully prepared by the interaction of 2- and 4-benzoylpyridine and the appropriate Grignard reagent according to Kenyon and Thakar¹. These tertiary alcohols containing 2- or 4-pyridyl as one of the groups have been allowed to react with (+)-tartaric acid or (+)-camphor-10-sulphonic acid to form the crystalline salts. On fractional crystallisations of these salts, it has been possible to resolve isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl and methylphenyl-4-pyridyl methanols. Attempts to resolve other seven pyridine carbinols by alkaloidal salts of half-acid ester method failed.

Preparation of ($\pm$)-Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.—Phenyl-2-pyridyl ketone (36.0 g.) in ether (200 ml) was added to the Grignard complex, prepared by taking Mg(9.6 g.), isopropyl bromide (49.2 g.), and ether (75 ml); working up of the contents by the usual methods provided the crystalline carbinol (24 g.), m.p. 70-72°. Other substituted methanols, prepared similarly, are recorded in Table I along with their physical characteristics and analytical data.

TABLE I
Pyridine methanols (α - and γ -substituted).

No.	Substituted methanols.	R.	C ₅ H ₄ N. C(OH)C ₆ H ₅ .R		n_D^{25} .	d_{20}^{25} .	[α] _D ²⁰ .	%Nitrogen.	
			Formula.	M.P. or B.P.				Found.	Reqd.
1.	<i>n</i> -Propylphenyl-2-P	<i>n</i> -Pr	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	61-62°	..	..	..	5.97	6.16
2.	Isopropylphenyl-2-P	<i>i</i> -Pr	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	70-72°	..	..	+106° (c, 2.2 in chloroform)	6.08	6.16
3.	<i>n</i> -Butylphenyl-2-P	<i>n</i> -Bu	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ ON	180°/22mm	1.5630	1.2629	..	5.72	5.81
4.	Isobutylphenyl-2-P	<i>i</i> -Bu	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	74-74°	..	..	..	5.69	5.81
5.	Isoamylphenyl-2-P	<i>i</i> -Amyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON	220°/12mm	1.5540	1.2380	..	5.28	5.49
6.	Methylphenyl-4-P	Me	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ ON	148-50°	..	..	+1.58 (c, 0.45 in methanol)	6.90	7.03
7.	Isopropylphenyl-4-P	<i>i</i> -Pr	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ ON	136°	..	..	..	5.98	6.16
8.	<i>n</i> -Butylphenyl-4-P	<i>n</i> -Bu	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ ON	119-20°	..	..	..	5.68	5.81
9.	Isoamylphenyl-4-P	<i>i</i> -Amyl	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ ON	117-18°	..	..	..	5.31	5.49

P denotes pyridyl-methanol.

Resolution of (±)-Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.—(+)-Tartaric acid (15 g.) was added to a solution of (±)-isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl methanol (22.7 g.) in warm ethanol (70 ml). The clear solution on keeping at the room temperature for 4 days separated a solid on partial decomposition; 20.1 g. (crop A), m.p. 120°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 19.7^\circ$. Crop A on further recrystallisation provided crop B (9.1 g.), m.p. 80-83°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 28.5^\circ$ on partly decomposing it. The crop B after further recrystallisation from ethanol furnished crop C (6.5 g.), m.p. 98°, which did not show any rise in rotation on further recrystallisation. The optical rotations are recorded below.

(+)-*Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.*—The less soluble crop C (6.0 g.) was taken in a separating funnel containing ice-water, decomposed with sodium carbonate solution (5%), and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed, dried (Na_2SO_4), and evaporated to provide the active carbinol; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 32.08^\circ$ (c, 2.81 in acetone), m.p. 90-92°. Further recrystallisation from ether-light petroleum did not increase the rotation. The optical rotations in other solvents are shown below:

- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 106^\circ$ (c, 2.2 in chloroform).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 83^\circ$ (c, 1.06 in benzene).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 81.7^\circ$ (c, 1.04 in toluene).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 40.8^\circ$ (c, 0.834 in ethanol).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 35.0^\circ$ (c, 0.795 in methanol).
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 30.3^\circ$ (c, 0.732 in dioxane)
- $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 37.7^\circ$ (c, 0.71 in methyl acetate).

(-)-*Isopropylphenyl-2-pyridyl Methanol.*—The filtrate A was decomposed after concentration to obtain the active carbinol; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 4.4^\circ$ (c, 10.15 in methanol). It did not increase in rotation by further crystallisation.

Resolution of (±)-Methylphenylpyridyl Methanol.—(+)-Camphor-10-sulphonic acid (7 g.) was added to a solution of (±)-methylphenyl-4-pyridyl methanol (6 g.) in warm ethanol (36 ml). The clear solution after keeping at the room temperature for 2 days deposited crop A (10.2 g.), m.p. 174.5°. It was taken in ethanol (26 ml) and set aside when it furnished crop B (8.35 g.), m.p. 179-81°. The crop B on further recrystallisation afforded crop C; m.p. 185-86° (4.8 g.).

(+)-*Methylphenyl-4-pyridyl Methanol.*—The less soluble crop C (4.8 g.) on decomposition by sodium carbonate (5%) provided the active carbinol; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.567^\circ$ (c, 9.45 in methanol); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2.114^\circ$ (c, 0.62 in benzene); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.765^\circ$ (c, 0.34 in toluene); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 3.08^\circ$ (c, 3.982 in chloroform); $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 1.13^\circ$ (c, 7.13 in ethanol).

(-)-*Methylphenyl-4-pyridyl Methanol.*—The more soluble fraction on concentration and on decomposition furnished the carbinol, m.p. 145°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 0.2^\circ$ (c, 5.3 in chloroform).

Van Camper² recorded m.p. of (±)-methylphenyl-4-pyridyl methanol as 140-42°.

The IR spectra of these carbinols were taken on a Beckman IR 4, by the courtesy of Saldter Research Laboratories, Philadelphia-2, PA.

Reactions of these pyridyl carbinol with 1-chloro-2-dimethylamino-ethanol (in inert solvent in presence of sodamide) are in progress.

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